

The Role of SWAYAM in Higher Education

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Abstract: India is a huge populated country in the world. It can be developed at faster rate by making the changes in higher education system by introducing the updated changes in the science, technology and new techniques in in teaching. Online mode of education is one to correct in the dis advantages or obstacles in existing higher education system. Advancement in Digital technology has become prominent role in higher education at present in the global level. In this context Indian government has given much priority to develop the human resources in India by introducing various novel programmes like SWAYAM, National Digital Library, SWAYAMPURABHA and National Academic Depository etc. SWAYAM has designed to achieve the cardinal educational principles of access, equity and quality It is a free online education and tries to provide best teaching learning resources to all. It plays an important role to provide high standard education to the Indian youth learners and strengthening higher education.

Key Words: SWAYAM, online education, technology, techniques, Digital revolution

1. INTRODUCTION:

India is a developing economy and it has the best demographic profile in terms of youth population. India's current population estimates nearly 125 crores. In which about 50 per cent of the population is below the age of 25 years and 65 per cent in total are below the age of 35. (1) It is a favourable advantage to India to gain the employment opportunities in the global employment market as India having high youth force. It is possible only by making the changes in higher education system or by introducing updated changes in Indian higher education system occurred at global level in science and technology and improved teaching techniques. This could be help in the overall development of the Indian youth. The higher education has becoming a focal point in the socio economic development of the society or a nation in recent years as it is a transforming the knowledge and its application. Hence the institutions of higher education make significant contribution to the socio economic development and growth of a nation through improving the innovations and skills of youth learners. Higher education is one of the strategic drivers of growth performer, prosperity and competitiveness. It creates a quality work force and provides an opportunity to a person to succeed in today's global economy. In developed countries the higher institutions are providing various suitable programmes of knowledge oriented, professional development and training to their students and preparing them for various sectors to stay and progress in the labour market in keeping with the changes in world economy. They assure the improvement of knowledge and build right skills that can help in the improvement of the economic wealth of nations, adapt workforce development and changing demand for new skills and thus support in the improvement of productivity and growth of the country. This can be achieved through the training of first-class minds, through introducing major developments of science and technology by encouraging interest in learning. The higher education at present is not fulfilling the needs of Indian society as still majority of the higher education institutions are implementing traditional system of Education. Further many feedback reports are expressing that classroom teaching and curriculum is not satisfying the learners.

2. STUDENTS OPINION MATTERS:

- “Teachers are not inspiring”. Class room transaction should facilitate bidirectional Process
- The Current Methodology of Teaching is for Getting Marks – not supporting all round development
- Information is abundantly available on all forms- Don't know how to use effectively. Need Guidance
- Constant Support / Mentoring is needed to support students opting for Online Courses
- Teacher Accessibility and Availability - Off Campus
- Train the Teachers on 21st Century Skills.

In the above situation, online education may overcome the above barriers and fulfil the needs of the present learners in India.

3. ONLINE PROGRAM:

Online mode of education is popularised in recent years in world wide. It can be more useful to the Indian education system as many higher education institutions are not in a position to inculcate the measures of higher standard of curriculum and teaching techniques. It is a way of learning source to fulfil the needs of youth learners in India. In this context Indian government has given much priority to develop the human resources in India by introducing various novel programmes like SWAYAM, National Digital Library, SWAYAMPBABA and National Academic Depository etc. The Indian Government has designed SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active Learning for Young Aspiring Minds) with the help of Microsoft to achieve the cardinal educational principles of access, equity and quality. SWAYAM seeks to bridge the digital divide for students by the digital revolution and create the knowledge economy. It is an Indigenous and free IT based massive open online courses platform. In this programme all courses are designed by the best teachers in the country and offering hundreds of courses with transferable credits.(2) These courses are available at free of cost to anyone, anytime and anywhere using the IT system from 9th class to post graduation. It tries to provide best teaching learning resources to all. Online mode of learning allows sharing of best quality education with faculty and everyone.

In the first phase IITs of Madras, Bombay, Guwahati, Kanpur, IIMs of Bangalore, Calcutta and Universities of Delhi, JLN, Banaras alone as well as with the help of faculty of foreign universities offered various courses in social sciences, energy, management, engineering education and basic sciences. At least One crore students are expected to benefit in 2 to 3 years through this initiatives. (3) SWAYAM provides online mode of Classroom. The online setting presents to the students with an opportunity to participate asynchronously in a learning environment by means of a virtual classroom, making this setting highly popular amongst students due to its convenience and flexibility. The self-pace characteristic of the online environment provides good opportunity for slower pace to gain education with minimal anxiety. In addition, the online classroom's asynchronous participation allows students contribute with more thoughtful comments adding value to the class discussion. Content, Pedagogy & Technology plays an integral role in online education. It plays an important role to provide high standard education to the Indian youth learners and strengthening higher education.

4. SWAYAM MOOCS ARE DEVELOPED & DELIVERED IN FOUR QUADRANTS:

- High Quality Video Tutorials & Multimedia Instructions: video Lectures by the best teachers with duration of 20 to 30 minutes each video.
- E –Content: Self Instructional reading material, e-Book, downloadable
- Assessments: Assignment s, quizzes, Problems and Solutions – for Self Evaluation
- Online Discussion forum: for posting queries and clarifying clearing the doubts.

5. FEATURES OF SWAYAM:

- High quality video lectures and learning material available for learners' at anytime and anywhere.
- One – stop internet based location for interactive e – content for all courses from high school to university level.
- Easy to access, monitoring and certification etc.
- The facility available for peer groups to interact and discuss for clarify their doubts.
- Swayam courses could facilitate to Blended learning model that adds to the quality of class room teaching instead of the traditional learning method.

6. WAYS TO BENEFIT FROM SWAYAM:

- Academicians through SWAYAM can facilitate effective teaching both On Campus & Online.
- A class teacher can act as Mentor to assist Online in Class;
- SWAYAM material may be used as Blended Learning or Flip Classes, a mix of classroom & online activities.
- An institution may allow whole class to opt a MOOC.
- Swayam courses provide an excellent course delivery methods unbound by location or time allowing for accessibility to instruction.
- The self-pace characteristic of the online environment provides good opportunity for slower pace to gain education with minimal anxiety.
- Online mode of learning allows sharing of best quality education with faculty and everyone.
- SWAYAM courses are available at free of cost to anyone, anytime and anywhere using the IT system from 9th class to post graduation.
- In this programme all courses are designed by the best teachers in the country and offering hundreds of courses.
- Universities / Colleges are approving credits issued in the certificates of completed courses under SWAYAM platform.

- Adult learners can access a course from their home from home computer via internet at their convenient time to reach their academic and career goals.
- SWAYAM Courses are available in Two Verticals
 - a) Student Vertical: Scheduled Courses & Self Pace Courses
 - b) Faculty Vertical: Scheduled Courses: ARPIT – Annual Refresher Programme for Teachers

7. SWAYAM COURSE LEVELS & COORDINATORS [STUDENT VERTICAL]:

Courses under SWAYAM are available at various levels and to maintain the best quality content and delivery for each level, nine National coordinators have been appointed. They are:

- AICTE (All India Council for Technical Education) for self – paced and global level courses.
- NPTEL (National Programme on Technology Enhanced Learning) for Engineering.
- UGC (University Grants Commission) for non-technical Post graduation Education.
- CEC (Consortium for Educational Communication) for under graduate Education.
- NCERT (National Council of Educational Research and Training) for school Education.
- NIOS (National Institute of Open Schooling) for school Education.
- IGNOU (Indira Gandhi National Open University) for out of school students.
- IIBM (Indian Institute of Management, Bangalore) for management studies.
- NITTTR (National Institute of Technical Teachers Training and Research) for teacher training programme.

8. KEY ELEMENTS OF A SUCCESSFUL ONLINE PROGRAM:

- Swayam programme is purely online mode of learning system. Hence internet is essential to utilise online courses. Need of Government initiation is essential to provide internet facility to rural India.
- Laptop / computers other electronic gadgets are needed to this learning mode of education which are more expensive to the rural poor. Hence, The Government should take initiation to provide Laptop / computers other electronic gadgets to the economically poorer section of the people at subsidized prices or affordable prices.
- Swayam programme to be developed in all regional languages to overcome the language barriers.

9. CONCLUSION:

Education is a focal point to change the economic development of a nation. India is also not exempt to it. Updated changes in science and technology are to be incorporate in education system for getting opportunities available in the present world market. Online mode of learning is more useful to prepare the Indian youth in a useful manner and also it is one to correct in the disadvantages or obstacles in existing higher education system. Advancement in Digital technology has become prominent role in higher education at present in the global level. Swayam is a suitable online education system for the present situation of India further faculty and students in higher education level will be updated by getting high standard education techniques and syllabus. It plays an important role to provide high standard education to the Indian youth learners and strengthening higher education. It leads to the development of India. Therefore, the government of India and national co-ordinators of all levels in the nation has to be taken some favourable steps to implement swayam in effective manner.

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